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614_Cambodian (Khmer)

Source:

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Huffman, Franklin Eugene. An outline of Cambodian Grammar
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I. Language Profile

Population: 12,110,065 in Cambodia (2004). Population total all countries: 13,276,639.

Region: Throughout the country. Also spoken in Canada, China, France, Laos, USA, Viet Nam.

Alternate names: Khmer, Cambodian

Dialects: Distinct from Northern Khmer of Thailand.

Classification: [Austro-Asiatic](#), [Mon-Khmer](#), [Eastern Mon-Khmer](#), [Khmer](#)

Language use: Official language. 1,000,000 second-language speakers.

Language development: 35% of the population over 15 cannot read or write Khmer. Script derived from a southern Indian alphabet. First written during the period of Indian influence. Grammar. Bible: 1954–1998.

Comments: SVO.

Viet Nam

Language name : Khmer, Central

Population: 1,055,174 in Viet Nam (1999 census).

Region: Mainly in Hau Giang, Tra Vinh, Vinh Long, Kien Giang, An Giang, Bac Lieu, Ca Mau, Ba Ria-Vung Tau, Binh Phuoc, and Tay Ninh provinces and Ho Chi Minh City.

Alternate names : Cambodian, Kho Me, Cur Cul, Cu Tho, Viet Go Mien, Khome, Krom

Dialects: Central Khmer, Southern Khmer.

Comments: Buddhist, Christian.

II. Morpheme Types

- no inflection for nouns and verbs
- verbal categories are expressed by means of particles: pre- or post-
- only in valence changing operations (verbs) and derivation there is prefixation and infixation

i. stem

ii. preposed restricted formative

- „prefixes“ of the same form can attach to N and V but with different functions:

ex.: p-

- when attached to V: CAUS, but also nominalization
/dac/ 'to break (intrans.)' > /pdac/ 'to break (trans.)'
/le:ŋ/ 'to play' > /ple :ŋ/ 'song, musical composition'
- when attached to N: verbalization
/ku:/ 'a pair' > /pku:/ 'a pair off'
- when attached to prepositions it derives adjectives
/daoy/ 'by, with' > /pdaoy/ 'right away'

iii. preposed unrestricted formative

- ex.: Cɔ- (reduplicative) 'attribution'
- derives adjectives from conjunctions: /dael/ 'that which' > /dɔ-dael/ 'the same'
- derives adjectives from nouns: /daəm/ 'origin' > /dɔ-daəm/ 'originally, at first'
- derives adjectives or adjectival verbs from verbs: /pe:n/ 'to cross the legs' > /po-pe:n/ 'criss-crossed'
- derives adjectival verbs from negative particles: /te:/ 'no, not at all' > /to-te:/ 'to be free, empty'
- derives adjectives from nouns: /cuə/ 'row, line' > /co-cuə/ 'in a row, dragging along'
- ex.: /qa:-/ 'derogation, diminutive'
- occurs productively with verbs, nouns, pronouns, demonstratives, adjectives, and its derivatives usually occur as derogatory terms of address, although they occasionally occur as terms of reference
- with V: /to:c/ 'to be small' > /qa:-to:c/ 'little one!, runt!'
- with nouns: /cao/ 'thief' > /qa:-cao/ 'you thief!'
- ex.: /preəh-/ occurs with a noun whose referent is of sacred and esteemed nature, and before any verb expressing action performed by a person of sacred and or high esteem

/put/ 'the Buddha' > /preəh-put/ 'the Buddha'

/sdaen/ 'to show, explain' > /preəh-sdaen/ 'to teach' (of the Buddha or the monks)

iv. Infixes

- derivation
- most of them attach to verbs
- unrestricted: /-b-/ 'specialization'

/lɒəŋ/ 'to try, test' > /lɒɔ:ŋ/ 'an experiment'

/lɛ:k/ 'time, occasion' > /lɒæk/ 'what can be accomplished in one attempt'

v. Postposed restricted formative

– very few, only derivation

vi. Postposed unrestricted formative

– very few, only in derivation

III. Phonological Word

– bound by two open junctures

– may contain from one to six syllables, with various stress patterns and syllable shapes

– great majority of words are monosyllabic

– polysyllabic words are usually loans

– monosyllabic words:

• any occurrence of a stressed syllable preceded and followed by an open juncture is a word

• monosyllabics containing a single vowel or a short diphthong occur in three canonical shapes: /C^ˈVC/, /CC^ˈVC/, /CCC^ˈVC/

• monosyllabics containing a long vowel or a long diphthong occur in five canonical shapes: /C^ˈVV/, /C^ˈVVC/, /CC^ˈVV/, /CC^ˈVVC/, /CCC^ˈVVC/ (only two instances)

– disyllabic words:

„minor disyllables“: any unstressed syllable followed in close juncture by a stressed syllable

• structure of stressed syllable as for monosyllabics

• unstressed syllable: C₁(C₂)V(C₃):

C₁ is any consonant except /f/, but only /p, t, c, k, s/ before C₂

C₂ is /r/

/V/ is any short vowel after C₁, but only /ə, a, o, ɔ/ after C₂

C₃ is any C except /b, d, f, r/

„major disyllables“: any stressed (primary or secondary) syllable followed in close or medium juncture by another stressed (primary or secondary) syllable

• no significant limitations on the shape of the first syllable

• morphologically simple major disyllables occur only in relatively careful speech, becoming minor disyllables in colloquial speech through loss of stress on the first syllable

• those major disyllables which occur in normal speech are usually complex, reduplicatives or compounds

– polysyllabic words: any sequence of more than two syllables between two successive occurrences of open juncture

• trisyllabic words: σòó; òóó; óóó; óóó; σóó

• quadrisyllabic words: σóóó; óσòó; óóóó; óòóó; óóóó; σóóó

- pentasyllabic words: $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$; $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$; $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$; $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$; $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$; $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$
- hexasyllabic words: $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$

IV. Syllable

structure of stressed syllable: $C_1(C_2)(C_3)V_1(V_2)(C_4)$ – if V_2 does not occur, then C_4 must occur

- C_1 represents any consonant which occurs as the initial phoneme of a stressed syllable: all can be initial - /p, t, c, k, b, d, f, s, h, ʔ, m, n, ŋ, η, w, y, l, r/
- C_2 represents any one of a sub-class of C_1 which occur after certain C_1 phonemes:
 - C_1C_2 sequences fall into three categories on the basis of the kind of transition which occurs between them: C_1C_2 ; $C_1^hC_2$; $C_1\theta C_2$
 - C_1C_2 : C_1 is /p, t, c, k/ and C_2 is /p, t, k, n, ŋ, η, w, l, r/
 - $C_1^hC_2$: C_1 is /p, t, c, k/ and C_2 is another voiceless stop or a continuant other than /r/, except for the sequence /kŋ/
 - $C_1\theta C_2$: in any sequence where C_2 is /b, d, ʔ/, any sequence where C_1 is /m, l/, and in the sequence /kŋ/ and /sn/
- C_3 represents the phoneme /h/ which may occur after /st/ and /lk/
- V_1 represents any vowel which may occur after C_1 phonemes:
 - any short vowel or short diphthong
 - when V_1 is not followed by V_2 , C_4 must occur
 - short diphthongs /eə, uə, oə/ occur only before C_4 and do not occur after /b, d, ʔ, f, s, h/
 - /i, e/ occur only before /ʔ, h/ as C_4 with one occurrence of /ey/
 - /eə/ occurs only before /ʔ, η, h/
 - /oə/ occurs only before /p, t, m, n, l, h/
 - /uə/ occurs only before /t, ʔ, n, η, h/
- V_2 represents any of a sub-class of V_1 which may occur after certain V_1 phonemes:
 - any V_1 may follow itself as V_2 except the short diphthongs /Və/
 - if V_2 is /ə/ V_1 is not /ɔ/
 - if V_2 is /e, o/ V_1 is /a/
 - /i:/ and /u:/ do not occur after /b, d/
 - /eə/ does not occur after /b, ʔ, s/
 - /oə/ does not occur after /b, ʔ/
- C_4 represents any one of a sub-class of C_1 which may occur after V_1 phonemes, or after a sequence of V_1V_2 : any consonant except /b, d, f, r/ with the following restrictions:
 - /p, t, m, n, l, h/ seem to occur after all vowels
 - /c, ŋ/ do not occur after /i, e, ɔ, eə, uə, i:, e:, i:, ɔ:, iə, ae, oə/
 - /w/ occurs only after /ə, a, o, i:, e:, a:, iə, eə, ae/
 - /y/ does not occur after /i, ɔ, eə, uə, oə, i:, e:, i:, u:, iə, ae/
 - /s/ occurs in final position only in a highly pedantic reading pronunciation, being replaced by /h/ in all other levels of formal and colloquial speech

- unstressed syllables: locus of greatest morphophonemic free variation; syllables tend to be levelled in colloquial speech to Cə

V. Phonological Processes

i. Vowel Lowering of /i/, /e/

lower allophones before /q/ and in unstressed syllables

ii. /i, e/ > [ɪ, ɛ] / _ /h/

iii. Lowering and Fronting of high back unrounded vowel

- grammar uses /i/ for the „high back unrounded“ vowel
- lowered and fronted before /c, ɲ/, approaches the quality of /e/

iv. Diphtongisation

/a, u, o/ > [aɪ, uɪ, oɪ] / _ {c, ɲ}

the same process applies to the long forms of the vowels

v. Ablaut

two correlative vowel series

series 1		series 2
əy	>	i:
ae	>	e:
ə:	>	ɪ:
aə	>	ə:
a:	>	eə
o:	>	u:
ao	>	o:
ɔ:	>	oə
e	>	i
ə	>	ɪ
a	>	eə before /q, n, h/ oə before /p, t, m, n, h/
o	>	u
ɔ	>	o in reduplicative prefixes u before /p, m/ uə elsewhere
ay	>	iy
aw	>	ow

- automatic ablaut is conditioned by phonotactic rules, e.g. by the non-occurrence of series 2 vowels after /b/ (no further information)

ex.: /le:ŋ/ 'to play' > [lbaeŋ] 'game'

vi. Vowel Harmony

– in many derivatives of disyllabic shape, the series of the affix vowel is determined by the series of the base vowel

a) reduplicative prefixes are of shape CV- where V is ɔ~ə or o~ə:

- Cɔ- occurs when the base vowel belongs to series 1
- Co- occurs when the base vowel belongs to series 2
- if C is a nasal or lateral, Co- occurs
- if C is a voiced stop /b, d/, or /s/, Cɔ- occurs

b) Prefixes of shape prV- 'reciprocity'

- pro- occurs sporadically before bases whose vowel occurs only in series 2
- prɔ- occurs elsewhere

c) prefix bɔN- ~ puəN- 'causation':

- puəN- occurs sporadically before bases whose initial C is /y, r, l/ and whose vowel occurs only in series 2
- bɔN- occurs elsewhere

d) infix -ɔm- ~ -um- 'causation'

- -um- occurs if the second C of the base is a sonorant, and the base vowel occurs in series 2
- -um- occurs also if the first C of the base is a sonorant
- -ɔm- occurs elsewhere

e) infixes of shape -ɔN- ~ -uəN- 'nominalization'

- -uəN- occurs if the second C of the base is a sonorant, and the base vowel occurs only in series 2

f) infixes of shape -ɔm(n)- ~ -um(n)- 'nominalization'

- -ɔmn- occurs in bases with a single initial C whose vowel belongs to series 1
- -umn- occurs in bases with a single initial C whose vowel belongs to series 2
- -um- occurs if the second C of the base is a sonorant and the base vowel belongs to series 2 or if the C of the base is a sonorant
- -ɔm- occurs elsewhere

g) infixes of shape -rV(n)- 'nominalization'

- -ron- occurs sporadically in bases with a single initial C, and whose vowel occurs only in series 2
- -rɔn- occurs in bases with a single initial C before other vowels
- -rɔ- occurs in bases with an initial consonant sequence

h) non-harmonic disyllables:

- when the vowels are not in harmony, the regular pattern is the occurrence of a vowel of series 1 in the first syllable, or affix, and a vowel of series 2 in the second syllable, or base; only a few forms have the reversed order

– in a smaller number of forms, the series of the base vowel is determined by the series of

the affix vowel, i.e. replaced by its correlative alternant in the same series as the prefix vowel

ex.: /muc/ 'to submerge' > [pɾmɔc] 'to put under'

vii. Alternations in unstressed syllables

– Vowel reduction: CV > Cə

ex.: /mo.núh/ > [mə.núh] 'human, man'

– /b, d/ > /p, t/

ex.: /dɔ.daél/ > də.daél > [tə.daél] 'same'

– /sɔ/ > sə > [tə]

ex.: /sɔ.sée/ > sə.sée > [tə.sée] 'to write'

– /rɔ/ > rə > lə > [qa]

ex.: /rɔ.bíən/ > rə.bíən > lə.bíən > [qa.bíən] 'method'

– CVq > CV > Cə

ex.: /piq.báaq/ > pi.báaq > [pə.báaq] 'difficult'

– Crɔ, Cro > Crə, Cə

ex.: /srɔ.nók/ > srə.nók > [sə.nók] 'peaceful'

– CVN > CəN > Cə

ex.: /kɔn.láeŋ/ > kən.láeŋ > [kə.láeŋ] 'place'

– reduction of an unstressed syllable of form CVN in rapid speech to a syllabic nasal

– ex.: /dɔn.dóp/ > dən.dóp > n.dóp (~ tə.dóp) '-teen'

ix. Devoicing: /b, d/ > [p, t] / _ N

ex.: /baek/ > [pnaek] 'fragment'

ix. Voicing: /p, t/ > [b, d] / _ ɔN

ex.: /prae/ 'to use' > [bɔmrae] 'servant'

x. /r/ > [rɔ] / _ C

ex.: /riən/ 'to study' > [robiən] 'knowledge'

VI. Suprasegmental Features

i. Stress

– domain: syllable

– four degrees: unstressed, secondary (in colloquial speech with function word; on the first constituent of many compounds whose second member bears primary stress; on the second constituent of a small set of compounds whose first constituent carries primary stress), primary (co-occurs with all primary or content words in an utterance and with syllables cited in isolation), contrastive

– stress reduction to the preferred minor syllable stress pattern in colloquial speech for disyllabics and polysyllabics, changes involves stress and vowel reduction:

– óóó > oóó; loss of stress can be correlated by loss of final C in unstressed

syllable

ex.: /qáq.k^hóo.sáq/ > [qa.k^hòo.sáq] 'future'

- óóó > òóó
- óóóó > óóóó
- óóóó > óóóó

ii. Juncture

- defined by contrasting degrees of syllable duration
- close juncture: preceding syllable has short duration, typically occurs after bound syllables with zero or secondary stress
- medium juncture: preceding syllable has medium-short duration and may carry secondary or primary stress; indicated usually a closer grammatical relationship between syllables than does open juncture; thus frequently occurring in compounds; it may however occur between bound syllable in deliberate speech
- open juncture (unmarked): preceding syllable has medium duration, and may carry either primary or secondary stress, but is never unstressed; defines the phonological word
- long juncture: preceding syllable has long duration, primary stress, and is usually accompanied by raised sustained pitch; indicates a major immediate constituent cut within an utterance

VII. Reduplication

i. reduplicative prefixes

- function: repetition, intensification, continuous action
- shape CV-, where C is a reduplication of the initial consonant of bases with initial /p, t, c, k, s, b, d, m, n, ŋ, ŋ/
- ex.: /kaay/ 'to dig' > /kɔkaay/ 'to dig around, scratch about'

ii. Total reduplication

- entire base is reduplicated
 - both constituents are based: onomatopoeic adjectives
 - both constituents free: plurality, generality, intensification
- ex.: /proh/ 'man' > /proh-proh/ 'men, men in general'

iii. Partial reduplication

a) Ablauted reduplicatives

- reduplication of the base with vowel ablaut
- patterns of vowel alternation are random, but certain alternations occur with relative frequency
- ex.: /te:ŋ-ta:ŋ/ 'incoherent, confused'

b) Rhyming reduplicatives

- reduplication of the nucleus and final consonant (if one occurs) of the base
- intensification

– ex.: /caoŋ-haoŋ/ 'to be rude, arrogant'

c) Alliterative reduplicatives

– reduplication of the initial consonant or consonant sequence of the base, or in the case of disyllables, of the prefix plus the initial consonant or consonant sequence of the base

– ex.: /prəm-prəy/ 'cute, likable'

iv. Incomplete reduplicatives

– rhyming reduplication of the second syllable of a disyllabic base

– ex.: /pɔpleh/ 'teasing' > /seh-pɔpleh/ 'frivolous, unprincipled'

/kɔndae-rae/ 'a kind of dance'